

Green Marketing Mix Elements Effect on the Environmental Sustainability Performance of Manufacturing Firms

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Received: Feb 28, 2026

Accepted: Mar 31, 2026

Published: Apr 04, 2026

Abstract

Environmental deterioration is generally the fault of organizations of all shapes and sizes. Manufacturing firms, on the other hand, are under pressure to implement measures to slow environmental deterioration, since they are seen as major sources of pollution. Hence, the study sought to assess the effects of the green marketing mix elements (product, price, promotion, and place) on the environmental sustainability performance of Manufacturing firms in two regions of Ethiopia. To achieve the intended purpose, information was collected from 350 respondents of these firms using a self-administered, closed-ended questionnaire. The study was conducted using the Partial Least Squares Structural Model (PLS-SEM). The study finds positive, statistically significant results for all predictive variables, with varying degrees of effect on environmental sustainability. Also, the study showed a substantial predictive relevance. Among them, green products have the strongest effect, while green place has the weakest effect on environmental sustainability. This study suggests that manufacturing firms should invest in green marketing practices, as this approach helps enhance environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Green marketing mix, environmental sustainability, manufacturing firms, Partial Least Squares, Structural Equation Model

1. Introduction

Businesses and legislators alike are making sustainability a top priority on their strategic agendas due to a growing worldwide concern about environmental degradation and climate change (Peattie & Crane, 2005). Because of its large ecological impact, the manufacturing sector has drawn the most attention from businesses. Also, Javeed et al. (2020) asserted that the manufacturing sector is among the most polluting in both developed and developing nations. To reduce this pollution and comply with sustainable development objectives, numerous manufacturing companies have started incorporating green marketing into their operations (Vehbi et al., 2025). Green marketing is used to encourage sustainable, environmentally friendly practices that help meet customer requirements (Durmaz & Yaşar, 2016; Apaza-Panca et al., 2024). Since environmental care has become more popular (Chung, 2020), green marketing, which uses practical techniques and components, helps to reinvent or innovate products or services to protect the environment, resources, and locations (Apaza-Panca et al., 2024). In addition to protecting the environment, green marketing also helps businesses build their reputation (Bahta et al., 2021), foster customer loyalty (Justavino-Castillo et al., 2023), reduce costs, and ultimately improve financial returns and business performance (Ren & Hussain, 2022). This contribution is crucial to sustainability across all spheres of business activity. Among them, environmental sustainability is an important one (Elkington, 2017). It stands as a fundamental component of sustainability (Said et al., 2024). It emphasizes the need to protect ecosystems for the benefit of future generations and argues that

meeting our demands shouldn't come at the expense of environmental quality (Kaswan et al., 2018). Additionally, it encompasses a range of programs, laws, and strategies aimed at promoting sustainable development, reducing environmental damage, and conserving resources (Tennakoon, 2024). More specifically, it includes initiatives to lower carbon emissions, save water, reduce waste, and safeguard ecosystems (Noiki et al., 2023). So, to be environmentally sustainable, implementing green marketing principles is a very wise choice. Even though the focus on green practices, such as green marketing, is becoming increasingly familiar, very few firms in the manufacturing sector of developing countries pay due attention to them (Puppim de Oliveira and Jabbour, 2017; Hassan & Jaaron, 2021; Braik et al., 2023). As recommended by Javeed et al. (2020), firms operating in the manufacturing sector of developing nations urgently need to implement green policies to reduce their environmental impact and meet growing customer demands. This implementation gap is also reflected in the scarcity of research on green marketing in developing countries (Garg, 2015; Yadav et al., 2016; Mehraj & Qureshi, 2020; Qureshi, 2020; Braik et al., 2023). Hence, using Ethiopian manufacturing companies, the study investigated the uncharted area of the interplay between the adoption of green marketing and ecologically sustainable performance.

Recent studies demonstrate how green marketing mix approaches in manufacturing businesses enhance environmental performance. Del Brío et al. (2007) discovered, for instance, that incorporating eco-design and cleaner distribution methods in Spanish manufacturers greatly increased waste reduction and energy efficiency. Braik (2023) found that the company's environmental performance (EP) improved through green placement and green products. As identified by Farradia et al. (2019), the sustainability environment performance is positively impacted by the green marketing mix. Similarly, (Akude et al., 2025) demonstrated how green products substantially improved environmental performance in emerging markets manufacturing contexts.

Considering the findings of previous researchers and the dearth of studies in developing countries' manufacturing contexts, this study aimed to assess the effect of green marketing mix elements practiced by Ethiopian manufacturing companies on environmental sustainability performance.

2. Literature review

2.1 Green product and environmental sustainability

Delivering safer or more hygienic products, repurposing, recycling, or dematerializing products, minimizing packaging materials, reusing, and enhancing the durability, reparability, composability, or disposability of products are all examples of green product strategies (Kinoti, 2011). Green products and environmental sustainability are positively and significantly correlated, according to empirical research. According to Braik et al. (2023) green products help businesses become more environmentally sustainable. The advantages of green products, according to (Kaur et al., 2022), including their higher quality and environmental performance, their capacity to protect the environment and not harm it, and their favorable impact on society's health. Green products are a fundamentally significant strategy that businesses utilize to address environmental problems and issues (Esmaelnezhad et al., 2023). Additionally, (Kaur et al., 2022) reflected that green products have a large environmental effect, and a considerable relationship exists between green products and environmental concerns (Davari & Strutton, 2014). This led to the development of the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1 (H1): Green Product has a significant effect on the environmental sustainability of Ethiopian Medium and Large Manufacturing firms.

2.2 Green price and environmental sustainability

A new generation of cost-conscious consumers has emerged, one that is willing to spend more on environmentally friendly items due to the declining quality of the environment and the urgent problems it is linked to, such as natural disasters and global warming (Joshi & Rahman, 2015; Hassan & Jaaron, 2021). However, green pricing activities as part of a green marketing strategy ensure that consumers can afford green products and urge them to be willing to spend more for them (Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017). In industrialized nations like Europe, consumers are becoming more willing to pay extra for environmentally friendly products; according to 75% of respondents, they would be happy to spend a little bit more for such goods (European Commission, 2014). Furthermore, Kirmani (2025) examined the elements that made Indian consumers more inclined to live sustainably and spend more on environmentally friendly goods. Also, they concluded that customers' environmental concerns were the driving force behind this readiness. As a result, it would seem that businesses in communities where environmental concerns are prevalent would be expected to take greater care of the environment (Kumar et al., 2017). Thus, the following hypothesis was proposed.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Green Price has a significant effect on the Environmental sustainability of Ethiopian Medium and large manufacturing firms.

2.3 Green Promotion and Environmental Sustainability

Promoting environmentally friendly goods and services has emerged as an essential component of companies' environmental performance objectives as green consumption has grown in popularity (Shabbir & Wisdom, 2020). By employing green promotion tactics, businesses can successfully inform stakeholders about their environmental preservation initiatives, commitment, and successes (Eneizan, 2020). Furthermore, the government promotes the idea of a green environment and increases public awareness of environmental protection through green advertising (Rahim et al., 2012). As noted by Chen & Chen (2015), a company can get a competitive edge over competitors by matching customer expectations and implementing green advertising, which is essential for improving the availability of environmental goods and services. Strong internal environmental competencies will be developed by organizations that emphasize and support green practices that can ensure environmental sustainability (Li et al., 2018). In addition to the aforementioned studies, Wahyuningtiyas & Novianto (2023) concluded that environmental sustainability is directly impacted by green promotion. Consequently, the following theory was created.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): Green promotion has a significant effect on the environmental sustainability of Ethiopian Medium and Large Manufacturing firms.

2.4 Green Place/Distribution and Environmental Sustainability

Manufacturers' supply chains heavily rely on green installation and distribution (Han et al., 2019). Green distribution and placement encompass all practices aimed at reducing the company's environmental effect throughout production and shipment (Mele et al., 2019). Also, Leonidou et al. (2013) state that green placement includes the recycling of materials, the reuse of products, and the customer's reverse logistics for used items. In addition to the previously specified issues, Sarkis et al. (2011) outlined two strategies to increase fuel consumption efficiency through green distribution: reducing the frequency of transportation operations and optimizing delivery routes. So, organizations can strengthen their environmental protection efforts by using these green practices. When we see the effect of green places on environmental sustainability, researchers like (Yildiz Çankaya & Sezen, 2019; Wahyuningtiyas & Novianto, 2023; Hejazi et al., 2023) identified a significant positive effect. By considering these points, we can hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Green place has a significant effect on the environmental sustainability of Ethiopian Medium and Large Manufacturing firms

3. Methods

3.1 Sampling, data source, and method of data collection

The number of manufacturing firms considered in the study was 189. The respondents from each manufacturing firm were selected. This study used the firm's management bodies as respondents. A total of 378 respondents were considered in this study. The reason for including only the management bodies was their exposure to the firm's activities, strategies, and performance. The number of items in the questionnaire can also be used to calculate the sample size; five to ten responders are sufficient for each item (Hair et al., 2014). The primary data sources were managers of manufacturing firms found in Ethiopia. To collect the required data, a survey instrument and a quantitative research approach were used. The survey instrument was created based on the literature review (Chan, 2013; Ko et al., 2013; Richey et al., 2014; Papadas et al., 2017; Chen & Yang, 2019).

3.2. Method of data analysis

The collected data were processed using Smart PLS3 Software, and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was used to analyze them. PLS-SEM was chosen because it is suitable for non-normal data (Ringle et al., 2012; Hair et al., 2014; Henseler et al., 2016). Compared to covariance-based SEM methods, PLS-SEM enables researchers to estimate extremely complex models with multiple constructs and indicator variables (Hair et al., 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2021; Magno & Ringle, 2024) and with significantly smaller sample size requirements (Ringle et al., 2012; Sarstedt et al., 2021; Subhaktiyasa, 2024).

4. Results

4.1 Assessment of measurement/ Outer Model

The outer model was evaluated to assess the internal consistency, reliability, and validity of the constructs. To measure factor loading's inter-item reliability, Cronbach's alpha was used. The outer loading values ranged from 0.615 (GRPL8) to 0.848 (GRPC1). But two indicators (GRPL 8 and GRPL 10) from the green place construct were removed since their value was lower than 0.7, and their omission led to improvement of construct reliability and convergent validity (Hair et al., 2017). So, the evaluation of all required measures was conducted after removing these two indicators. Since most construct values exceeded the required threshold, indicator reliability was achieved (see Table 1). Also, multicollinearity was assessed by using the VIF values of each indicator. This value ranged from 1.619 to 3.233, indicating that multicollinearity was avoided (see Table 1). To evaluate internal consistency, Cronbach's Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR) were used. The CA values ranged from 0.886 to 0.892, and the CR values ranged from 0.904 to 0.912. This indicates that construct reliability has been achieved for this study (see Table 1). To measure convergent validity, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was employed. Convergent validity helps to determine the degree of contribution of the items in the representation of a construct (Ren and Hussain 2022). So, the average variance extracted values for each construct ranged from 0.505 to 0.654, which exceeded the 0.5 acceptable threshold (Hair et al., 2020) (see Table 1).

Table 1: Outer Loadings and Reliability

Construct	Item	loading	CA ^a	CR ^b	AVE ^c	Outer VIF
Green product	GRPT1	0.767	0.887	0.909	0.557	2.024
	GRPT2	0.757				1.914
	GRPT3	0.739				1.796
	GRPT4	0.763				1.852
	GRPT5	0.752				1.870
	GRPT6	0.718				1.714
	GRPT7	0.730				1.752

	GRPT8	0.742				1.815
Green price	GRPC1	0.848	0.867	0.904	0.654	3.027
	GRPC2	0.790				1.872
	GRPC3	0.828				2.501
	GRPC4	0.727				1.678
	GRPC5	0.845				3.233
Green promotion	GRPN1	0.812	0.886	0.911	0.594	2.137
	GRPN2	0.784				2.059
	GRPN3	0.810				2.258
	GRPN4	0.729				1.816
	GRPN5	0.789				2.023
	GRPN6	0.743				1.782
	GRPN7	0.722				1.789
Green place	GRPL1	0.767	0.892	0.912	0.566	1.999
	GRPL2	0.718				1.619
	GRPL3	0.766				2.143
	GRPL4	0.715				1.711
	GRPL5	0.777				1.866
	GRPL6	0.764				1.890
	GRPL7	0.769				2.037
	GRPL8	0.717				1.918
	GRPL9	0.717				1.918
Environmental Sustainability	ENVS1	0.703	0.892	0.911	0.506	2.354
	ENVS10	0.716				1.981
	ENVS2	0.706				2.381
	ENVS3	0.701				2.182
	ENVS4	0.714				1.732
	ENVS5	0.713				1.935
	ENVS6	0.716				2.458
	ENVS7	0.718				1.685
	ENVS8	0.716				1.718
	ENVS9	0.710				2.136

The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio and the Fornell-Larcker criterion were used to evaluate discriminant validity. The correlations between the constructs and other model constructs must be less than the square root of AVE for each variable (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). All of the bolded and italic values in Table 2 were greater than the intercorrelation variables, according to the study's findings. The variables may therefore be regarded as having sufficient validity.

Table 2: Fornell–Larcker criterion

	Environmental sustainability	Green place	Green price	Green product	Green promotion
Environmental sustainability	0.711				
Green place	0.218	0.752			
Green price	0.407	0.129	0.809		
Green product	0.458	0.135	0.279	0.746	
Green promotion	0.349	0.143	0.162	0.072	0.771

According to Table 3 below, the constructs' Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio values were significantly lower than the permissible cutoff of 0.85(Hair et al. 2019) with the maximum value of 0.506. Thus, discriminant validity was achieved in this study.

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio

	Environmental sustainability	Green place	Green price	Green product	Green promotion
Environmental sustainability					
Green place	0.225				
Green price	0.451	0.140			
Green product	0.506	0.148	0.315		
Green promotion	0.379	0.151	0.181	0.109	

4.2 Assessment of Structural Model/Inner Model

The structural/inner model was evaluated using paths between the exogenous and endogenous constructs (Ren and Hussain 2022). Collinearity, Path coefficients, Explanatory power (R^2), effect size (f^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), and model diagnostics are among the important factors that go into a thorough structural model evaluation (Hair et al., 2019).

Using bootstrapping with 5,000 subsamples, the path coefficients and their significance levels were estimated. The result of the bootstrapping and the hypothesis tested were presented in Table 4. The two-tailed test criterion (p -value<0.05) was used to determine whether to accept or reject a given association. As shown in Table 4, the effect of green place was positive and significant ($\beta = 0.099$), with very weak strength, indicating that for a 1% change in practicing the green place idea, environmental sustainability will change by around 1%. Green pricing showed a significant positive relationship ($\beta = 0.252$) with environmental sustainability. This implies that a unit change in green pricing of manufacturing firms will lead to the enhancement of environmental sustainability by 25.2%. The green product showed the most positive and significant influence ($\beta = 0.355$) on environmental sustainability. This means that when there is a 1-unit increase in firms' production of green products, their environmental sustainability will increase by 35.5%. Lastly, the correlation between green promotion and environmental sustainability was positive and significant ($\beta = 0.268$). Also, a unit change in communicating about green practices will improve environmental sustainability by 26.8%.

Table 4: Hypothesis testing

Proposed relationship	Path coefficient	SD	T- value	P- Values
Green place-> Environmental sustainability	0.099	0.042	2.358*	0.018
Green price-> Environmental sustainability	0.252	0.047	5.329**	0.000
Green product-> Environmental sustainability	0.355	0.046	7.782**	0.000
Green promotion-> Environmental sustainability	0.268	0.047	5.763**	0.000

Note: *t-value > 1.96, and ($p < 0.05$) **<0.01.

With regard to the explanatory power (R^2), it should explain ≥ 0.10 (10%) of the variation(Falk and Miller, 1992). So, in our case, the green marketing mix elements collectively explained 0.380 (38%) of the variance in the firm's environmental sustainability performance (see Table 5 and Figure 1). When we see the predictive relevance (Q^2), its value should be>0 (Hair et al, 19). So, the predictive relevance value for this study was 0.348, which exceeded the proposed acceptable limit. Therefore, this study demonstrated substantial predictability. Table 5 also displays the size effect. The values of the impact size (f^2) ranged from 0.015 to 0.186. According to the Cohen (1988) criterion, green places had a small relative impact on environmental sustainability ($f^2 = 0.015$), green prices had a medium relative impact ($f^2 =$

0.092), green products had a medium relative impact ($f^2 = 0.118$), and green promotion had a medium effect ($f^2 = 0.112$). To evaluate the Goodness of fit, this study used the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), which is proposed by (Henseler et al., 2014; Hair et al., 2019). Henseler et al. (2014) state that SRMR is an absolute measure of fit, with a value <0.08 indicating good fit and 0 indicating perfect fit (Hair et al., 2019). As a result, this study's SRMR score was 0.059, well below the necessary cutoff. This indicates that the model fitness of this investigation is satisfactory (see Table 5).

Table 5: Explanatory power (R^2), Predictive relevance (Q^2) and Effect size (f^2)

Predictors	f^2	Out come	R^2	Q^2	SRMR
Green place	0.015	Environmental sustainability	0.380	0.348	0.59
Green price	0.092				
Green product	0.186				
Green promotion	0.112				

Figure 1: Path coefficients and R^2

5. Discussion

The structural model analysis's findings shed important light on how the green marketing mix components, green place, price, product, and promotion affect environmental sustainability. All hypotheses proposed for this study were accepted since all of the suggested relationships were determined to be significant (all p-values were below 0.05, and T-values were over 1.96) (see Table 5).

The first hypothesis showed a significant effect of green product on environmental sustainability ($\beta = 0.355$, $t = 7.782 > 1.96$, $p = 0.000 < 0.001$); hence, H1 was accepted. For this study, a relatively strongest effect on environmental sustainability came from green products. This implies that creating and distributing eco-friendly products is essential to achieving long-term environmental results. This involves creating goods that are recyclable or biodegradable, employ renewable resources, and produce little waste. Also, this finding was compatible with other previous research results (Bhardwaj et al., 2020; Braik et al,2023; Ntongai Jeremiah and Bonke, 2023).

The second hypothesis, H2, was also supported by fulfilling the required criteria ($\beta = 0.252$, $t = 5.329$, $p = 0.000$). Hence, green price demonstrated a moderate, statistically significant effect on environmental sustainability. This result suggests that price policies that account for

environmental costs are crucial tools for advancing sustainability. For manufacturing firms, this entails offering competitive prices for eco-friendly products, utilizing cost-based pricing models that account for sustainable inputs, and considering environmental externalities into pricing. This conclusion about the association between green pricing and environmental sustainability is also compatible with the conclusions of Jewdaly et al. (2024); Hayat et al. (2019); Setyawati et al. (2020); Sana (2020).

Concerning the effect of green promotion on environmental sustainability, H3 was proposed. Also, this hypothesis was supported ($\beta = 0.268$, $t = 5.763$, $p = 0.000$) and accepted, as it met the required criteria. This result demonstrates a significant and relatively substantial effect. This finding emphasizes the significant role of communication in uplifting sustainability efforts. Product differentiation in competitive marketplaces, enhanced brand reputation, and stakeholder confidence can all be achieved through effective green promotion. The study findings by Wahyuningtiyas and Novianto (2023), Hartmann et al. (2023), and Jewdaly et al. (2024) are similar to this study.

The finding shows a relatively small but statistically significant correlation between environmental sustainability and green place ($\beta = 0.099$, $t = 2.358$, $p = 0.018$). This implies that, from an organizational perspective, environmentally friendly choices in plant site selection, warehousing, supply chain routing, and distribution logistics do impact environmental sustainability. The smaller path coefficient, however, suggests that these initiatives may have less impact or be less noticeable than other green marketing mix components. For industrial companies, green location strategies such as partnering with green-certified logistics suppliers or streamlining transportation routes to reduce carbon emissions may still be in their infancy or face practical challenges. This study's findings on how green spaces affect environmental sustainability aligned with the findings of other similar studies (Wahyuningtiyas & Novianto, 2023; Braik et al., 2023; Ntongai Jeremiah & Bonke, 2023; Campus et al., 2023; Fraj et al., 2011)

6. Conclusion

Drawing on insights from managers of manufacturing firms, this study examined how the green marketing mix elements (place, price, product, and promotion) affect environmental sustainability. The results show that these four elements have a significant impact on environmental sustainability outcomes, with the strongest effects observed in green product and green promotion. These findings highlight the significance of incorporating environmental considerations into core marketing and operational strategies. For manufacturing companies, this entails prioritizing environmentally friendly, efficient distribution systems, responsible pricing strategies, clear environmental communication, and sustainable product innovation. In addition to improving their environmental performance, companies that implement a comprehensive green marketing strategy strengthen their competitive advantage and long-term viability in a sustainability-driven market.

7. Limitations and implications for future research

Although this investigation offers useful information, it is worth highlighting its drawbacks. The findings might not be as generalizable to other sectors, such as services, retail, or agriculture, because the data were collected only from managers of manufacturing companies. Therefore, the researcher asked other researchers to evaluate the suggested approach across several sectors. Second, the study's cross-sectional methodology limited the capacity to infer causality because it recorded perceptions at a single point in time; hence, researchers can use a longitudinal design to observe change over time. Third, the study used only a quantitative approach. Therefore, it is recommended that future research use mixed-methods and qualitative approaches to identify the green marketing strategies that most affect environmental performance. Last but not least, the study examined only four components of the green marketing mix; it did not cover other potentially important variables, such as green people

(internal culture), green packaging and labelling, green process, and green physical evidence, which may be the subject of future studies.

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